

A REVIEW ON POLYCYSTIC OVARIAN DISEASE

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ABSTRACT

Women of reproductive age are affected by the common endocrine illness PCOD and PCOS the health of women is greatly affect by PCOD and PCOS which can cause a wide range of symptoms and outcome the formation of ovarian cysts and the production of immature eggs are the hallmark of PCOD is associated with complication such as infertility, metabolic syndrome, obesity, insulin resistance, and cardiovascular risks. this review explores the etiology, pathophysiology, clinical manifestation, diagnostic criteria pharmacological management strategies of PCOD the review also discusses recent advancement in treatment and highlights the crucial role of pharmacist inpatient care and education nowadays positive outcomes are obtained from the treatment and management of polycystic ovarian syndrome using herbal, allopathic and unani approaches because they address a range of issues associates with the condition, whether they are genetic or metabolic

Natural medication, especially those from plants is the least harmful, most readily available, and effective means of treating ailment nowadays.

KEYWORDS: PCOD, Polycystic Ovarian Disease, PCOS, Polycystic Ovary Syndrome, Endocrine Disorder, Hormonal Imbalance, Androgen Excess, Insulin Resistance, Ovarian Dysfunction, Irregular Menstrual Cycle, Anovulation, Metabolic Syndrome, Obesity, Infertility, Reproductive Health, Follicular Cysts, Hyperandrogenism, Acne, Hirsutism, Alopecia, Lifestyle Modification, Pharm, Pharmacological Management, Oral Contraceptives, Anti-androgens, Metformin, Treatment Approaches, Diagnosis, Ultrasonography, Ovulatory Disorders, Menstrual Irregularities, Women's Health, Long-term Complications, Cardiovascular Risks, Type 2 Diabetes, Weight Management, Evidence-based Therapy, Clinical Management, Pathophysiology.

INTRODUCTION^[1,2,3,4]

Fig. 1: Polycystic Ovarian Disease.^[5]

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a common hormonal disorder that affects women of reproductive age worldwide. It is marked by abnormal ovarian activity, increased levels of male hormones, problems with insulin action, and irregular ovulation. Studies suggest that nearly one in ten women develop PCOS before reaching menopause, often experiencing ongoing reproductive and metabolic difficulties. Although hormonal irregularities—such as a higher luteinizing hormone (LH) to follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) ratio and changes in gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) secretion—are considered important features of PCOS, the exact biological causes of the condition are still not completely understood. Research indicates that PCOS develops due to a combination of factors, including insulin resistance, excess androgen production, genetic and epigenetic influences, and environmental factors. In addition, women with PCOS have an increased likelihood of developing long-term

health problems such as cardiovascular disease type 2 diabetes mellitus metabolic syndrome and mental health disorders, including depression and anxiety.

Weight reduction of at least 5% is considered a key component in the management of this condition. Consequently, women with PCOS are advised to engage in consistent physical activity and adhere to diets low in fat and added sugars. In addition, some individuals choose complementary and alternative therapies, either as standalone options or in combination with conventional treatments, due to factors such as cultural beliefs, affordability, or perceived benefits.

In clinical practice, commonly used pharmacological options include combined oral contraceptives, anti-androgen medications, insulin-sensitizing agents, and drugs that induce ovulation.^[4] However, there is currently no treatment specifically approved by the United States Food and Drug Administration (USFDA) for PCOS.

Common symptoms^[6,7,8,9,10,11,12]

Fig 2:- Symptoms of PCOD.^[13]

A. Androgen Excess from Ovarian and Adrenal Sources

Polycystic Ovarian Disease is marked by increased production of androgens originating from the ovaries and, in many cases, the adrenal glands. More than half of women with PCOD

show elevated adrenal androgen levels, particularly dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate (DHEAS). Despite extensive research, the exact cause of adrenal androgen overproduction has not been clearly identified. Excess androgen plays a central role in the development of clinical symptoms such as acne, excessive hair growth, and menstrual disturbances.

B. Insulin Resistance and Metabolic Dysfunction

Insulin resistance is considered a fundamental mechanism in the development of PCOD. Women with this condition commonly exhibit reduced tissue responsiveness to insulin along with increased circulating insulin levels. Elevated androgens further intensify insulin resistance in peripheral tissues.

At the cellular level, insulin resistance in PCOD is linked to defects in insulin receptor signaling after insulin binding, especially in skeletal muscle and adipose tissue. Obesity significantly worsens metabolic and reproductive abnormalities, including hyperandrogenism, infertility, and menstrual irregularities. Approximately 30–60% of women with PCOD are obese, with a body mass index exceeding 30 kg/m², and show pronounced hyperinsulinemia. However, insulin resistance is also present in lean women with PCOD, and increasing body weight further aggravates this condition.

C. Neuroendocrine Dysregulation

PCOD is a complex neuroendocrine disorder affecting approximately 5–20% of women of reproductive age and represents one of the most common causes of female infertility. Alterations in gonadotropin secretion are a hallmark feature, including increased frequency and amplitude of luteinizing hormone (LH) pulses and an elevated LH to follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) ratio.

These abnormalities are thought to result from enhanced pulsatile release of gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH). GnRH neurons contain estrogen receptor- β but lack androgen and progesterone receptors. Consequently, steroid hormone feedback on GnRH secretion occurs indirectly through other hypothalamic neurons.

D. Abnormal Gonadotropin Secretion and Androgen Overproduction

In PCOD, excessive LH stimulation of ovarian theca cells leads to increased synthesis of androgens such as testosterone and androstenedione. Due to chronic anovulation,

progesterone levels remain insufficient to suppress GnRH pulse activity, resulting in continued LH secretion and reduced FSH production.

This hormonal imbalance disrupts normal follicular development and promotes persistent androgen excess. Reduced sensitivity of the hypothalamic GnRH pulse generator is believed to contribute to the onset of PCOD during adolescence. Elevated androgen levels are observed in nearly 60–80% of affected women.

E. Ovulatory Dysfunction and Endometrial Effects

Disordered follicular maturation in PCOD leads to increased secretion of anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) from granulosa cells. Persistent anovulation causes reduced progesterone output and prolonged estrogen exposure.

The absence of progesterone-mediated opposition to estrogen increases the risk of endometrial hyperplasia and carcinoma. Lower FSH levels further impair follicle maturation, resulting in amenorrhea and infertility. Additionally, excessive LH secretion contributes to ovulatory failure and increases the risk of miscarriage in women with PCOD.

Causes of PCOD^[14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21]

Fig. 3: Causes of PCOD.^[22]

1 Insulin Resistance

Insulin resistance is a prominent metabolic feature of PCOS and is commonly accompanied by compensatory increases in circulating insulin levels. Elevated insulin enhances androgen synthesis in the ovaries and interferes with normal ovulatory function. Insulin directly stimulates ovarian theca cells, which are involved in androgen biosynthesis, leading to

increased testosterone production. This interaction between insulin resistance and androgen excess contributes significantly to reproductive dysfunction in PCOS.

2 Hyperandrogenism

Hyperandrogenism results from excessive androgen production caused by disrupted ovarian activity and metabolic abnormalities such as insulin resistance. High androgen levels negatively affect follicular growth by preventing proper maturation of ovarian follicles and suppressing ovulation. This hormonal imbalance is responsible for many clinical manifestations of PCOS, including menstrual irregularities and infertility.

3 Inflammation

Low-grade chronic inflammation plays an important role in the development of PCOS. An imbalance between pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines, along with genetic variations affecting cytokine expression, may contribute to disease pathogenesis. Adipose tissue acts as an endocrine organ by releasing inflammatory mediators, promoting a persistent inflammatory state. Inflammatory processes stimulate excessive ovarian androgen production, and increased androgen levels further enhance abdominal fat accumulation, intensifying inflammation in PCOS.

4 Obesity

Obesity contributes to PCOS by enhancing luteinizing hormone-mediated stimulation of ovarian theca cells, resulting in increased androgen secretion. Elevated androgen levels disrupt normal menstrual cycles and further promote weight gain. This creates a self-perpetuating cycle in which obesity and hyperandrogenism worsen both metabolic and reproductive abnormalities associated with PCOS.

Management of PCOD^[23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33,34,35]

management of polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) should be guided by the individual needs, expectations, and priorities of each patient. Treatment goals may vary widely, ranging from fertility enhancement and menstrual cycle regulation to weight management and improvement of hyperandrogenic manifestations such as acne, excessive hair growth, or androgen-related hair loss. Consequently, therapy must be personalized to achieve optimal clinical outcomes. Since no single treatment strategy is effective for all patients with PCOS, current management primarily focuses on controlling symptoms rather than providing a definitive cure.

1 Weight Reduction

Excess androgen production in PCOS is closely associated with increased body weight, particularly central adiposity. Women with PCOS commonly exhibit abdominal fat accumulation, resulting in an android or “apple-shaped” body pattern rather than the typical gynoid distribution. Therefore, weight loss through caloric restriction is considered the cornerstone of PCOS management.

Research indicates that even modest weight loss—approximately 5–10% of total body weight—can significantly improve menstrual regularity and ovulatory function. Achieving a body mass index (BMI) within the normal range is especially beneficial for overweight and obese individuals. Weight reduction is also associated with decreased free testosterone levels and a lower risk of developing metabolic complications, including metabolic syndrome and insulin resistance.

2 Dietary Interventions

Dietary recommendations for women with PCOS should be individualized to align with personal goals and metabolic profiles. Nevertheless, general nutritional principles can be applied to improve metabolic and hormonal outcomes. A balanced diet rich in dietary fiber and low in saturated fats and refined carbohydrates is widely recommended.

Carbohydrates can be categorized based on their glycemic index (GI), which reflects their effect on postprandial blood glucose levels. Low-glycemic-index foods are preferred, as they help maintain stable blood glucose and insulin levels. These include whole grains, legumes, vegetables such as broccoli and carrots, soy products, lentils, bran-based cereals, and whole-grain bread. In contrast, high-glycemic-index foods—such as white rice, sugary desserts, refined baked goods, and processed snacks—should be limited, as they may worsen insulin resistance and exacerbate PCOS symptoms.

3 Supplementation

In addition to conventional pharmacological therapies, several nutritional supplements have demonstrated potential benefits for some women with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS). Commonly studied supplements include vitamin D, resveratrol, alpha-lipoic acid, omega-3 fatty acids, berberine, folic acid, myo-inositol (MI), and d-chiro-inositol (DCI). These agents may help improve metabolic, hormonal, and reproductive abnormalities associated with PCOS.

Vitamin D supplementation has shown positive outcomes in multiple studies, particularly during seasons with limited.

4 Pharmacological Treatments

Prior to initiating drug therapy, all women diagnosed with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) should be advised on lifestyle modification, including balanced nutrition and regular physical activity, irrespective of body mass index, symptom profile, or reproductive intentions. In many patients—particularly those with mild to moderate disease—lifestyle changes alone may lead to substantial improvement in clinical symptoms. When pharmacological intervention becomes necessary, treatment should be individualized based on the patient's clinical presentation and personal treatment goals. For women who do not intend to conceive and whose primary concern is menstrual irregularity, hormonal therapy is typically recommended. Combined oral contraceptives (COCs) or progestin-only preparations are commonly used to regulate the menstrual cycle. The choice of contraceptive may also take into account other PCOS-related manifestations. Certain formulations, such as those containing antiandrogenic components, may help suppress excess androgen production and can therefore be beneficial in managing symptoms like hirsutism and acne.

Metformin, a biguanide-class antidiabetic medication, is frequently prescribed as an adjunct to first-line hormonal therapies. Its primary mechanism involves enhancing insulin sensitivity, which can contribute to the restoration of ovulatory function in women with PCOS. In addition to its metabolic benefits, metformin has been shown to exert short-term antiandrogenic effects, further supporting its role in the comprehensive management of PCOS.

CONCLUSION

Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is a common health condition that affects both the reproductive system and metabolism in women. It develops due to a combination of genetic factors and lifestyle or environmental influences. The disorder involves several body systems, including hormonal control mechanisms, excess male hormone production, reduced insulin sensitivity, and abnormal fat tissue function. Differences in how these processes are affected explain why symptoms and disease severity vary from one woman to another.

Recent progress in genetic studies and improved methods for measuring steroid-related metabolites have helped researchers better understand the biological complexity of PCOS.

These findings suggest that PCOS is not a single uniform disease but a group of related conditions with different underlying causes. This understanding supports the possibility of personalized monitoring and long-term management, especially for reducing future heart and metabolic risks.

Better knowledge of the underlying disease mechanisms also opens the door to developing more targeted treatments. However, further research is needed before these therapies can be widely used. Large-scale, well-planned, and patient-focused clinical studies are required to evaluate newer treatment options, such as drugs targeting neuroendocrine pathways, kisspeptin-based therapies, and medications originally used for diabetes. These advances may improve treatment outcomes and overall quality of life for women with PCOS.

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